

THE ROLE OF THE ACHIEVEMENTS OF FINNISH EDUCATION IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract. *The preschool education stage is the first phase of continuous education, during which a child develops both physically and mentally. It is the stage where the foundation for the child's educational journey is established. This article analyzes methods and processes based on Finnish experience that can be implemented to enhance the quality and effectiveness of preparing children for school. Recommendations are made for adopting these methods. Today, drawing lessons from foreign experiences and creatively integrating them into practice, developing regulatory documents, educational methodological literature, and educational-methodical complexes according to contemporary demands, and forming modern management and pedagogical technology knowledge and skills for leaders and specialists of preschool educational institutions based on advanced foreign experience, are considered pressing issues.*

Keywords: *preschool education, Finnish education system, efficiency, quality, method, technique.*

It is important to suggest about that nowadays, drawing lessons from international experiences and creatively integrating them into practice, developing regulatory documents, educational methodological literature, and instructional-methodological complexes in accordance with contemporary demands, as well as equipping leaders and specialists in preschool educational institutions with knowledge and skills in modern management and pedagogical technologies based on advanced foreign practices, are considered pressing issues. To further improve the preschool education system, ensure equal access to quality preschool education for all children, and develop the non-state sector of preschool education services, the concept for the development of preschool education in the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030, in accordance with the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 30, 2018, "On Measures to Improve the Management of the Preschool Education System" (PD-3955), includes the following provisions of further improvement of the regulatory framework in the field of preschool education;

-creation of conditions for comprehensive intellectual, moral, aesthetic and physical development of preschool children;

-increase the coverage of children with quality preschool education, ensure equal access to it, develop public-private partnerships in this area;

-introduction of innovations, advanced pedagogical and information and communication technologies in the preschool education system;

-improvement of the preschool education management system, ensuring transparency and efficiency of financial activities of preschool education organizations;

-introduction of completely new approaches to training, retraining, advanced training, selection and development of employees of the preschool education system;

-ensuring healthy and balanced nutrition and quality medical care for children in preschool educational institutions.

There is very little literature and research papers on the study of the best practices of foreign countries in preparing children for school. In this regard, only electronic resources are available; they can be found and translated on various websites on the Internet.

The main goal of education in Finland is to ensure access to quality educational services for all children, regardless of their social background, to prepare them to grow up as active citizens of society and lead an independent life. Free pre-school education and general secondary education are guaranteed for everyone in the country.

The Finnish education system includes the following stages:

1. Pre-school education: pre-school education aimed at pre-school education and childcare, as well as preparation for general secondary education (up to 7 years);
2. General secondary education: primary and basic secondary education;
3. Secondary vocational education: general secondary vocational education or vocational education and training;
4. Higher education;
5. All stages of secondary education.

In Finland, pre-school education is free and compulsory for all children. Pre-school education aims to develop children's learning and self-development skills and plays an important role in preparing them for the next stage – comprehensive school.

The Finnish education system aims to offer equal educational opportunities for everyone. The most important priorities in the field of education have been defined by educational experts in the country: to view education as a tool for balancing inequalities in society, to provide students with free meals, health care and psychological counselling services during their studies. Also, according to the relevant legislation, depending on the need, students can be provided with a means of transport or accommodation for attending school. In addition, medical services are provided free of charge if a student is injured on school premises, during lessons or other educational activities, while going to or returning from school, and in a dormitory.

It is important to note that almost all schools in Finland are public and receive equal funding from the state. In-depth teaching of individual subjects or the creation of separate schools for certain subjects is not considered appropriate. Each student is considered to have unique talents, and their education and assessment are based on an individual curriculum. Students are not comparable. This creates the basis for stress-free student learning.

Preschools play an important role in many countries, but in Finland they are special and unique. Preschools in Finland accept children from 9 months to 6 years old. The Finnish education system is known worldwide for its high-quality education, but there are no uniform standards for preschool education. Each institution independently develops its own educational program. Children can stay with the family until they are 3 years old, but in most cases, parents are busy with work and send their children to preschools from an early age. Kindergartens are open from 06:00 to 17:00, in addition, there is 1 kindergarten in Jyväskylä that is open 7 days (1 week). Children are taught numbers and letters, but Preschools do not teach reading and writing.

There is an organic cooperation between parents and teachers at preschools. Parents will be informed one week in advance about what the children will be doing and what food they will be eating. A booklet with this information will be placed on each child's shelf one week before.

According to Finnish law, the number of children in a group is from 8 to 14. For every 4 children under 3 and for every 7 children from 3 to 6 years old, there is 1 teacher or kindergarten

teacher. The monthly fee for the kindergarten is fixed and is determined based on the monthly income of the parents. In addition, there is a notice board in each corner of the classroom. There are photos of the children's activities during the day, and parents can find out what their children have been doing during the day. There are no nurses or doctors in these kindergartens, if there are any changes in the children's health, the parents will be notified. One of the parents has the right to look after the child in case of deterioration in health. From an early age, the child develops skills in standing in line, caring for the environment, housekeeping, working in a team.

In Finnish preschools, children's daily life is enriched with various activities. Preschools take children outside every day. Such walks and visits to various cultural institutions are an integral part of the lessons. Groups usually consist of 12-20 children of different ages. One teacher can work with a maximum of 4 children, which is determined by law. Preschools in Finland are usually open from 06:30 to 17:00. However, parents have the right to leave their children for 4-5 hours. In addition, some preschools are open at night. These institutions are specially designed for cases when parents have to travel or work at night. Preschool in Finland is not compulsory. A third of preschoolers do not attend these institutions. In large cities, there are often not enough places for preschools, so parents who raise a child at home are paid 500 euros.

Summary. The preschool education system in Finland strives to create high-quality and flexible conditions for children. Night institutions are an important part of this system and serve to meet the various needs of parents. This system can be an interesting experience for other countries.

REFERENCES

1. Petri Lunaskorpi. "Teach like a Finnish teacher: Less workload - more results". OOO "Science and Innovations". Tashkent - 2023.
2. Durdona T., Fayzullaev S.N. METHODOLOGY OF DEVELOPING CHILDREN'S CREATIVITY IN PRESCHOOL GROUPS // SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL OF SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT AND LEADING RESEARCH ONLINE. - 2023. - Vol. 3. - no. 3. - P. 148-14
3. Fayzullaev S.N. et al. THE ROLE AND SIGNIFICANCE OF VARIATIONS OF THE PROGRAM "PATH OF SCIENCE" IN PREPARING CHILDREN FOR SCHOOL // ONLINE SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL OF SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT AND LEADING RESEARCH. - 2023. - Vol.
4. Fayzullaev S.N., Eshnazarova G. Integration of the problem-based learning method and innovations in education // ACADEMICIA: International interdisciplinary research journal. - 2019. - Vol. 9. - no. 1. - P. 60-65.
5. Fayzullaev S. Kh. SOCIAL AND PEDAGOGICAL FEATURES OF TRAINING CHILDREN'S TEACHER-COACHES TO WORK IN COLLABORATION WITH PARENTS // ONLINE SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL OF EDUCATION AND DEVELOPMENT. ANALYSIS. - 2022. - Vol. 2. – no. 1. – P. 179-182.
6. Fayzullaev S. N. SOCIAL AND PEDAGOGICAL FEATURES OF DEVELOPING THE COMPETENCE OF FUTURE SPECIALISTS IN PREPARING CHILDREN FOR SCHOOL // ONLINE SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL OF EDUCATION AND DEVELOPMENT. ANALYSIS. - 2022. - Vol. 2. – no. 1. – P. 172-175.

7. Jaloliddinova Maftunakhan Makhmudjanovna (postgraduate student of the faculty of preschool and primary education of Fergana State University). Pedagogical foundations of preparing children for school education in preschool educational organizations. International scientific journal "Science and Innovation" Volume 1 Issue 7 Uif-2022: 8.2 | ISSN: 2181-3337. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6578549>